

健康
畜禽

Healthy
Livestock

HEALTH PLANS AS ALLIES

WPI Biosecurity / Poultry / Health Plans Effectiveness

HEALTHY LIVESTOCK

Using antimicrobials in animals contributes to the rise and spread of antimicrobial resistance. By doing so it reduces the availability of safe and effective medicines against infectious diseases for both humans and animals. HealthyLivestock is a research project aiming to find ways to reduce the need to use of antimicrobials in livestock by improving the health and welfare of the animals.

BIOSECURITY

“Biosecurity is the prevention of disease-causing agents entering or leaving any place where they can pose a risk to farm animals, other animals, humans, or the safety and quality of a food product”.

Good biosecurity should be practiced at all times, not just during a disease outbreak. Taking the right measures in the early stages of a disease can help prevent or reduce its spread.

SYSTEMATIC AND STRUCTURED HEALTH PLANS

Achieving and maintaining a high broiler health state is essential for poultry farms sustainability. Healthy broilers limit the risk of farm economic losses, because of improved performance, reduced mortality and treatment costs. Keeping healthy broilers in farms can avoid major economic losses for the poultry industry. For instance, highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) viruses can kill up to 90-100% of the flock. The 2003 outbreak of HPAI (H7N7 virus) in the Netherlands led to the destruction of around 30 million birds and direct economic costs estimated at more than €150 million.

Furthermore, maintaining broilers healthy ensures a part of animal welfare, which is an important consumer concern. One way of achieving and maintaining a high broiler health state is the farmers' compliance with veterinarians' recommendations. Veterinarians' recommendations are intended to achieve a good health state. Despite this supposed relevance, no health improvements can be observed if farmers have difficulties to comply with formulated recommendations.

Tailor-made health and/or welfare plans include farm-specific recommendations adapted to farmers' objectives. Most of the recommendations in pigs and poultry are related to preventive measures, including biosecurity.

HEALTHYLIVESTOCK ON HEALTH PLANS IN POULTRY

This study describes the use of a novel BEAT, the BEAT, to identify strengths and weaknesses in biosecurity on broiler farms based on the FAO 3-zone model.

This assessment was used as a base to formulate a tailor-made health plan for each farm in the Netherlands, Greece, and Cyprus. It was made with SMART way by the veterinarian and the farmer and then checked by the researcher, aiming at improving animal health and as a consequence, reducing antimicrobial use.

It contained a list of interventions per zone which were aimed at strengthening on-farm biosecurity.

Estimations were made whether the interventions were long, medium or long term and if their costs were low, medium or high.

The health plans were implemented after the second cycle and evaluated after the fourth cycle. At the end of the fourth cycle, the farmer and veterinarian determined whether the interventions had been implemented or not and researchers assigned each intervention in the health plans to a category of a zone of the BEAT tool.

RESULTS

- Most interventions were planned for the green zone (303), followed by the orange-green zone (117), the orange zone (104), the red-orange transition zone (77), and the red zone (32).
- After the fourth cycle, 75.2, 36.3, and 23.0% of the interventions were realized in the Netherlands, Cyprus and Greece, respectively.
- Of all interventions, most were interventions that could be realized on the short term and were low in cost (n = 222).
- The realization rate at the end of the study was highest for low cost - short/medium term interventions (53 and 51%, respectively), and lowest for interventions with high costs and long term (1%).

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WHAT CAN YOU DO YOURSELF?

From April 2021, Article 25 of the European Union Animal Health Law, Regulation 2016/429 shall be implemented and it requires operators to make sure that establishments receive animal health visits from a veterinarian.

The creation of systematic and structured health plans is as important as obtaining feedback on them that lead to follow up actions.

Assessment with BEAT is a good starting point for the making of tailor-made health plans for each farm, in agreement with farmers and their vets responsible for herd health, including targets that could be checked and updated in the medium and long term as an ongoing process.

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If you want to know more about this topic visit <https://rebrand.ly/WP1HealthPlansPoultry> or scan this QR code